

PROFITABILITY ANALYSIS OF BLACK SOAP PRODUCTION IN EKITI STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the profitability of black soap production in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Primary data were collected using structured interview schedule from 90 respondents in a 3-stage sampling technique covering three local government areas of Ekiti State. Descriptive statistics was used to describe the socio-economic characteristics of producers, while soap profitability was computed using Gross Margin analysis. Factors affecting soap production was determined using multiple regression analysis. The results from the findings showed that majority of the respondents were females, married, experienced with average age of 56 years. It also revealed that they sourced credit from personal savings. The profitability analysis showed that a black soap producer incurs an average Total Cost (TC) of ₦21,404.67 and makes average Total Revenue (TR) of ₦23,724.67 with an average profit of ₦2,320.00 per production cycle. Therefore it can be concluded that black soap production is profitable in the study area. Results of multiple regression analysis showed that cost of production materials including palm kernel, packaging materials, ashes and fire wood were significant at different probability levels indicating that an increase in each variable leads to an increase in sales revenue. The estimated coefficient of multiple regressions (R^2) indicates 75% in the variation of sales revenue. The major constraints to black soap production were lack of capital, inadequate raw materials and non availability of water. The study recommended appropriate training and capacity building for soap producers as well as provision of facilities and other critical infrastructures to mitigate the constraints.

KEYWORDS: Socio-Economics, Profitability, Black soap, Production and Constraints.

INTRODUCTION

Soap has been known for years now. People in Nigeria had prepared their soap from the available technology found in their localities. There was no general way of making soap in those days because black soap was the most common form of soap then even as at present. On comparative physical evaluation, black soap has higher quality when compared to conventional soap in attributes such as appearance, colour, odour and texture (Samantha, 2004). Black soap is suitable for all skin types. It is also suitable for treatment of problems on dry, rough and moderate skin. Black soap reduces the discomfort that is associated with diseases like psoriasis and eczema, and can be used in removing makeup and any chemical that can blemish the skin. It is also beneficial for cleaning the hair. Black soap, unlike other soaps, is a versatile skincare product that offers multiple benefits and uses unlike other soaps which cannot be traditionally used on the body unless specifically categorised as facial or hand products. Black soaps can be used from head to toe as desired. It can either be used for body bathing, laundry or general cleaning of the human environment. Human beings can do without the use of soap. (Samantha, 2004).

The cheap price of black soap as a traditionally produced commodity enables people of different tribes and economic status to buy and use it. It is a widely used commodity that supports local economies in poor communities. The production of black soap can be done with ease because it requires little capital and simple technology. Black soap is produced using wholesome ingredients that are essentially considered as the “fruits of the earth”, thus making black soap production more distinctive and significant. Kathy (2009), revealed that black soap contains different ingredients. These includes nature's most bountiful gifts such as palm oil, coconut oil, palm kernel oil, ashes from various plants, (including shea tree bark, cocoa pods, banana husk, plantain leaves) and water. All these ingredients can be found all over the world. Human beings cannot do without the use of soap.

In Nigeria, statistics has shown that there are over eight thousands registered soap producers in the country. (Soap and detergent Manufacturer) (Akwaese, 2003). This however excludes other unknown individual producers found in many parts of the country (Ojiako, 2000). The famous black soap is now being used in many civilized countries but its secrets have not been fully understood over the years because of the wonderful and

amazing benefit it has on human body. Black soap making can be an essential activity in empowering our rural population, but carries its vocational hazards. The process can be hazardous to the producer at various stages of development due to the alkaline content. But the end result can both be rewarding and useful, provided an experienced black soap maker can create the finished products that can meet the desired characteristics of the end users. The technology for black soap production is not complex; therefore errors or mistakes during the separation process can easily be reclaimed or reversed or reclaimed. The major challenge of black soap making is the flip side of its moisturizing effects because it possesses such a high degree of glycerine which requires that it must be kept dry and covered in a small container in between uses at all times. Soap makers must be mindful of this habit in order to maintain the quality specifications desired of the soap. As a result of this, it is worthwhile to carry out the economic analysis to reveal its extent of profitability and viability in generating income. Soap production is a job that has reached advanced stage in Nigeria.

Problem Statement

In Nigeria today, the quantity of black soap being produced is not commensurate to the amount needed to satisfy the needs of the people. Certain groups of people especially the rural populace have been so addicted to the use of black soap that they cannot but use it in their daily activities. Furthermore, research reveals that 99% of those involved in the production of black soaps are women due to the low investment required in the process (Keith, 2007). It could then be regarded as an age-long traditional income-generating activity that confers self-sufficiency on producing households. Despite the fact that the ingredients required for the production are satisfactorily available, the unit price is low compared to what it ought to be.

Generally, there has been very little research and documentation as regards the profitability of black soap production. Product prices are very low and uncompetitive thus serving as a dis-incentive to those engaged in its production. Black soap production is a traditional enterprise that can be used to enhance and address rural poverty especially among the women if fully supported. According to Marsden (2009), the shortage of foreign exchange and restriction from importation of modern equipment to produce the soap on a large scale has negatively affected the profitability of black soap making. Osunbiyi (2009) reported that the unit cost of production of black soap has increased due to high rate of inflation, high cost of equipment and materials for production.

There has been no definite or specific method of production of black soap in Nigeria. The colour, texture and quality vary from one community to another across Nigeria. The potential for black soap production and utilization in Nigeria is huge however, the general belief that black soap is meant for poor people and the dark complexioned sets a drastic limitation. (Kathy 2009). Black soap production in neighbouring Ghana employs highly improved technology, and the soap is being exported into Nigeria thus yielding the country foreign exchange (Buchan2010). It therefore becomes imperative that some economic research be carried out to see how black soap production can be properly documented, especially its income generating capacity, and profitability. The broad objective of the study is to determine the profitability of black soap production in the study area. The specific objectives of the study include:

- Describe the socio-economic characteristics of black soap producers in the study area,
- Examine profitability of black soap production in the study area,
- Investigate the determinants of black soap in the study area ,and
- Identify constraints to black soap production in Ekiti State

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in three Local Government Areas of Ekiti State, Nigeria namely; Ikere- Ekiti, Emure-Ekiti and Ise – Ekiti. The state is located on longitude $4^{\circ}2$ and $5^{\circ}4E$ and latitude $6^{\circ}2$ and $8^{\circ}1^N$, with an estimated population of about 2,384,212 and land area of 10,898.8km² (NPC, 2006). The rainy season in the state is between March and October. Agriculture is the main stay of the State's economy. The major cash crops grown are cocoa, oil palm and plantain. According to Bamigboye and Kuponiyi (2009) the preponderance of these crops with by-products useful as raw materials for black soap production is one of the reasons why black soap production is common in Ekiti State. The state is also noted for production of root and tubers including yam, cassava.

A three stage sampling procedure was used in the selection of respondents for the study. In the first stage, three (3) local government areas (LGAs) noted for production of oil palm and cocoa were purposively selected based on ADP production figures. In the second stage, three communities having highest production figures for the

forementioned crops were selected purposively from each LGA making a total of 9 communities. Simple random sampling procedure was used in the third stage for the selection of 10 respondents from each community making a total of 90 respondents for the study. The community Association Register was used to draw the sampling frame.

Primary data was collected using structured interview schedule as instrument. The secondary data was gathered from journals, past projects, conference proceedings and the internet. The instrument captured questions covering the socio-economic characteristics of black soap producers, the cost of production, and the constraints. Data relating to socio-economic characteristics and constraints were analyzed using descriptive statistics like means, frequency counts and percentages. Profitability of black soap production in the study area was computed using the model. (Adegeye & Ditto 1985, Essentials of Agricultural Economics)

$$Profit = TR - TC$$

$$TC = TFC + TVC$$

TR = Total Revenue

TC = Total Cost

TFC = Total fixed cost

TVC = Total variable cost

The fixed inputs include local incinerator furnace, drums, pot, weighing scale, wheel barrow while variable inputs include palm kernel, firewood and packaging materials. Multiple Regression analysis was used to determine the factors influencing black soap production. The implicit form of the regression model specified is presented by the equation:

$$Y = f(X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4, X_5, X_6, X_7, X_8, \dots, U_1)$$

The explicit function in linear format is presented by equation

$$Y = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + b_5X_5 + b_6X_6 + U_1$$

Where: Y = dependent variable

X's = independent variable

b's = regression coefficient to be estimated

Y = quantity of black soap produced (kg)

X₁ = Age

X₂ = Education

X₃ = Cost of Palm Kernel

X₄ = Cost of Cocoa Pod Ashes

X₅ = Cost of Gathering Materials

X₆ = Cost of Water

X₇ = Cost of Packaging Materials

X₈ = Cost of firewood

U₁ = Error term

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-Economic Characteristics

The Socio-economic characteristics of the respondents are shown in Table 1. Analysis of the Table shows that majority (62.2 percent) are within the age range of 41-60 years, with only 4.4 percentages above 80 years. This implies that majority are in their productive age. The table further shows that black soap production is essentially women activity engaging 93.3 percentage women. Majority of the respondents (72.2 percent) are married with 62.2 percentages having household size of 5 or below. Those having household size of between and 6 and 10 members constitute 26.7 percent. Generally, large household sizes imply that more family labour

could be made available for soap production. As for educational attainment, Table 1 shows that 61.1 percentages have no formal education, followed by 23.3 percent who have primary education. The low level of literacy has implications for extension as education is known to be a weapon for change and it is directly related to the level of information dissemination, adoption, transfer and application of agricultural innovations (Achem and Akangbe 2011). 35.6 percent of respondents have between 21 and 30 years experience in black soap production. The years of experience and native wisdom may make up for their deficiency in education. Generally, experience is known to have positive effect on managerial capacity, technical knowhow and adoption of extension policies.

Table 1: Socio-Economic Characteristics of the Respondents N=90

Variables	Description	Frequency	Percentage
Age	≤40	5	5.6
	41-60	56	62.2
	61-80	25	27.8
	>80	4	4.4
	Total	90	100.0
Gender	Male	6	6.7
	Female	84	93.3
	Total	90	100.0
Marital Status	Single	4	4.4
	Married	65	72.2
	Divorced	6	6.7
	Widowed	15	16.7
	Total	90	100.0
Household Size	≤5	56	62.2
	6-10	24	26.7
	11-15	8	8.9
	>15	2	2.2
	Total	90	100.0
Educational Level	No Formal Education	55	61.1
	Primary School	21	23.3
	Secondary School	6	6.7
	University	8	8.9
	Total	90	100.0
Years of Experience	≤10	11	12.2
	11-20	20	22.2
	21-30	32	35.6
	>30	27	30.0
	Total	90	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2011

Profitability and Determinants of Soap Production

The result of the profitability analysis in Table 2 shows that gathering materials accounted for 13.06% of total variable cost while burning materials accounted for 11.35% of (TVC). The table also reveals that palm kernel cost accounted for 31.07% while cost of ashes accounted for 16.66% of the total variable cost. On the other hand, cost of firewood, pot, pan and water accounted for 8.87%, 5.16%, 5.50%, and 2.08% respectively. The analysis further reveals that cost of burning materials, palm kernel, ashes, firewood, pan, pot, and water gulped, 11.46%, 27.25%, 14.61%, 9.96%, 7.78%, 9.96% and 4.53% respectively of the total revenue (TR). This indicates that an average producer earned ₦2, 320.00 profits per production cycle which is profitable in the study area.

Table 2: Profitability Analysis of Black Soap Production

ITEM	AMOUNT(₦)	% OF TVC	% OF TR
Gathering Materials	244,650.00	13.06	11.46
Burning Materials	212,600.00	11.35	9.96
Palm Kernel	581,850.00	31.07	27.25
Water	38,920.00	2.08	1.82
Ashes	312,000.00	16.66	14.61
Pan	96,690.00	5.16	4.53
Pot	103,090.00	5.50	4.83
Firewood	166,150.00	8.87	7.78
Packaging Materials	116,900.00	6.24	5.47
Depreciation (Depre.)	535,69.89	2.86	2.51
Total Variable Cost (TVC)	1,872,850.00	100	90.22
Total Cost = TVC +Depre.	1,926,420.00		
Total Revenue (TR)	2,135,220.00		
Profit=TR-TC	208,800.10		
Profit/producer	2,320.00		

Source: Field Survey, 2011

Table 3 shows the multiple regression method that factors affecting black soap production in the study area using linear, semi log and double log functional forms of the regression model. The estimated functions were evaluated in terms of statistical significance of the coefficient of the multiple determinations (R^2) as indicated by F- value, the significance of the coefficient and the magnitude of standard errors. Based on the statistical and economic analysis carried out, the double log functional form was selected as the lead equation. Among the explanatory variable of the model are cost of palm kernel, packaging materials, ashes, and gathering materials which were significant at different profitability level. This implies that increase in the quantity of these variables would lead to an increase in sales revenue of the respondents, all things being equal. The result shows that estimated coefficient of multiple determinations (R^2) indicates that the postulated repressors' explained 75% in the variation of the regress. (i.e. black soap production).

TABLE 3: MULTIPLE REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Variables	Linear regression	Semi-log regression	Double-log regression
	coefficients	Coefficients	Coefficients
Constant	6760.75 (172.34)	6790.98 (677.33)	3.84 (0.032)
Age (X_1)	-0.004 (0.007)	-0.353 (0.323)	0.058 (0.061))
Educational level (X_2)	-0.003 (0.015)	0.111 (0.557)	-0.008 (0.016)
Cost of palm kernel (X_3)	0.071 (0.199)	0.700 (0.919)	0.539 (0.175)
Cost of Ashes(X_4)	0.001 (0.000)	0.300 (1.098)	0.320 (0.209)
Cost of Gathering Mat (X_5)	0.00 (0.000)	0.236 (0.279)	0.380 (0.53)
Cost of packaging mat (X_6)	0.006 (0.00)	0.561 (0.387)	0.940 (0.74)
Cost of fire wood (X_7)	0.002 (0.000)	1.354 (0.371)	0.235 (0.070)
Cost of water (X_8)	0.002 (0.000)	0.008 (0.248)	0.003 (0.047)
Adjusted R	0.126	0.355	0.466
Standard Error	0.629	0.525	0.998
R^2	0.204 (0.629)	0.507 (0.526)	0.750 (0.999)
F-value	2.599	3.344	7.750

Source: Field Survey, 2011

Constraints

The constraints to production of black soap are shown in Table 4. The result reveals that 48.9% of respondents are constrained by inadequate raw materials for production. This is followed by lack of capital (44.4percent) and water (34.4percent). Other factors like weather, land tenure system etc account for 13.3 percent.

Table 4: Constraint to Black Soap Production

S/No	CONSTRAINTS	FREQUENCY*	PERCENTAGE
1.	Capital	40	44.4
2.	Raw Materials	44	48.9
3.	Water	31	34.4
4.	Others	12	13.3

*Multiple responses Source: Field Survey, 2011

CONCLUSION

Generally, the study revealed that black soap production in the study area is a profitable enterprise. Being an activity dominated by women, promotion of black soap production can therefore be a veritable enterprise that could enhance the income and livelihood of the rural poor. In that case, emphasis can be placed on increasing the scale of production, improving the quality and competitiveness of production in order to promote its utilization by the elites.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on findings from the study, the following recommendations are made:

- Improving the technology of black soap production in order to maximize the economics of scale and also meet the requirement of elite users of the product.
- Provision of credit facilities at a lower interest rate to serve as encouragement for producers; stringent conditionality's for accessing such facilities should be removed.
- Appropriate training and capacity building especially in the areas of quality specifications and entrepreneurs management should be provided for soap makers.
- Provision of extension agents to disseminate new information to the producers by ADP and other Government organs.

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